

REVIEW OF VIRECHANA KARMA IN CLASSICAL TEXTS OF AYURVEDA

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Abstract

The Ayurvedic management of diseases consists of Shodhana and Shamana treatments. Shodhana Chikitsa is performed mainly by employing Panchakarma, it includes, Vamana, Virechana, Asthapana Basti, Anuvasana Basti and Nasyakarma. Virechana is considered as the best treatment for morbid and increased Pitta Dosh. This paper serves as a collection of references pertaining to Virechana Karma during ancient period of Ayurveda Samhitas, along with some information on the method of Virechana Karma explained in ancient textbooks of Ayurveda Samhitas.

Keywords: Shodhana; Panchakarma; Virechana; Purgation.

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1. Introduction

The Ayurvedic management of diseases in general, can be broadly grouped in to Shodhana and Shamana treatments. The former is intended to eliminate excessively vitiated Doshas out of the body and there by eradicates disease as a whole, while the later is directed towards palliation of vitiated Doshas. However, Ayurvedic classics unequally give paramount importance to the Shodhana therapy, owing to its credential of providing a complete cure. Acharya Charaka says that Doshas subdued by Langhana and Pachana therapies may provoke, but in case of Shodhana, there is seldom possibility of such recurrence.[1]

The Shodhana has got no parlance in the modern medicine, but we can say that the toxins and metabolic toxic products responsible for the disease are eliminated from the body. Shodhana Chikitsa is performed mainly by employing Panchakarma, it includes- Vamana, Virechana, Asthapana Basti, Anuvasana Basti and Nasyakarma.[2]

In the classics the Shodhana is specially indicated in Bahudoshavastha as a curative measure, in Rutucharya as preventive measure and prior to Rasayana Prayoga as a promotive measure.[3]

Virechana is less stressful procedure than Vamana Karma. It has less possibility of complications and could be done easily. So it is widely used as Shodhana therapy in routine. It is more acceptable to all classes of patients. In an addition to the acceptability and popularity, the Virechana is considered as the best treatment for morbid and increased Pitta Dosha.

2. Objectives

To collect references of Virechana Karma explained in Ancient Ayurveda Samhitas and to establish the method of Virechana Karma practiced in Samhita Kaala.

3. Material and Methods

This paper serves as a collection of references pertaining to Virechana Karma during ancient period of Ayurveda Samhitas, along with some information on the method of Virechana Karma explained in ancient textbooks of Ayurveda Samhitas.

Virechana Karma

Etymological Consideration

The word Virechana has three components. (Vachaspatyam 4847)

- Vi - Upasarga (prefix)
- Richir - Rich Dhatu (root)
- Lut - Pratyaya (suffix) (Maladi Nissaranam) Here 'Richir' – evacuation

Rich - Viyojana (separation)

Samparchana (combination)

The words 'Praskandana' and 'Rechana' are also used for Virechana Karma in classics.

Definition

Tatradoshaharanam Adhobhagam Virechana Sangyakam/ Cha.Ka. ¼, The act of expelling Doshas through 'Adhobhaga' is known as Virechana.[4]

Karyakshetra (site of action) of Virechana Dosha

Pitta, Pitta Sthanagata Alpa Kapha, Kapha Sthanagata Bahu Pitta, Pittavrita Vata, Sannipatika condition. (Bhela)

Dushya

Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Asthi, Majja, Shukra.

Strotas

Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, Asthivaha, Majjavaha.

In all the above Dhatu Vikaras Virechana is described in direct or indirect way.[5][6]

Table 1: Virechana Yogya Roga [7],[8],[9],[10]

Virechana Yogya	Ch.Sa	Su.Sa	As.Sa	As.Hr	Sh	BP& YR
Pitta Pradhana Vyadhi						
Jwara	+	+	+	+	+	+
Pandu	+	+	-	-	+	+
Kamla	+	-	-	+	-	-
Halimaka	+	-	+	+	-	-
Netradaha	+	+	-	-	-	-
Asyadaha	+	+	-	-	-	-
Paittik vyadhi	+	+	+	-	-	-
Vata Pradhana Vyadhi						
Pakvashaya Ruja	-	+	+	+	-	-
Shirahshoola	+	-	+	-	-	-
Parshvaruja	+	-	-	-	-	-
Gulma	+	+	+	+	+	+
Vatarakta	+	+	+	+	+	+
Kapha Pradhana Vyadhi						
Prameha	+	+	-	-	+	+
Netrasrava	+	-	-	-	+	+
Asyasrava	+	-	-	-	+	+
Nasasrava	+	-	-	-	+	+
Swasa	+	-	-	-	-	-
Kshavathu	+	-	-	-	-	-
Kasa	+	+	-	-	+	+
Tridoshaja Vyadhi						
Kushtha	+	+	-	-	+	+
Visarpa	+	+	-	-	-	-

Hridroga	+	+	-	-	+	+
Rakta Pradhana Vyadhi						
Pliha	+	+	+	+	+	+
Vyanga	+	-	+	+	-	-
Nilika	+	-	-	-	-	-
Visphota	+	+	+	+	+	-
Manasa Roga						
Unmada	+	-	-	-	-	-
Apasmara	+	+	-	-	-	-
Striroga						
Yonidosha	+	+	+	+	+	+
Shalya Kriya Sadhya Vyadhi						
Arbuda	+	+	-	-	-	-
Bhagandara	+	+	+	-	+	+
Arsha	+	+	+	+	+	+
Vidradhi	-	+	+	+	+	+

Granthi	+	+	-	-	+	+
Galaganda	+	-	-	-	-	-
Bradhna	+	-	-	-	-	-
Dushtavrana	-	+	+	+	-	+
Vridhhi	-	+	-	-	-	-
Apachi	+	-	-	-	-	-

Shalakya Vyadhi						
Timira	+	+	+	+	-	-
Abhishyanda	-	+	+	+	-	-
Kacha	-	+	+	+	-	-
Akshipaka	-	+	+	-	-	-
Annavaha Srotas						
Krimikoshtha	+	+	+	+	+	+
Garvisha	-	+	-	+	+	+
Visuchika	+	+	-	-	+	+
Alasaka	+	+	-	-	-	-
Udara	+	-	+	+	+	+
Arochaka	+	+	-	-	+	+
Avipaka	+	+	-	-	+	+
Vibandha	-	+	+	+	-	-
Anaha	-	+	-	-	-	-
Margabheda						
U.Raktapitta	+	+	+	+	-	-
Udavarta	+	-	+	-	-	-
Chhardi	+	+	+	+	+	+
Others						
Retodosha	+	-	+	+	-	-
Mutraghata	+	+	+	+	+	+

Shastrakshat a	-	+	-	-	-	-
Ksharagni dagdha	-	+	+	-	-	-

Table 2: Virechana Ayogya Roga

Virechana Yogya	Ch.Sa	Su.Sa	As.Sa	As.Hr	Sh	BP & YR
Incapable to tolerate the stress of therapy						
Vilambita	+	-	+	-	-	-
Durabala	+	-	-	-	-	-
Durbalendriy a	+	-	-	-	-	-
Upavasita	+	-	-	-	-	-
Subhaga	+	-	-	-	-	-
Alpagni	+	+	+	+	+	+
Abhihata	+	-	-	-	-	-

Kshatakshina	+	+	+	-	+	+
Shrant	+	+	-	-	+	+
Pipasita	+	+	-	-	+	+
Karma Bharadvaha ta	+	+	-	-	-	-
Vruddha	+	-	-	-	+	+
Bala	+	+	+	-	-	-
Atikrisha	+	-	+	-	+	-
Atisthula	+	+	+	-	+	-

Daruna koshtha	+	-	+	+	-	-
Kshama	+	-	-	-	-	-
Garbhini	+	+	-	-	-	-
Bhakta	+	+	-	-	+	-
Riktakoshtha	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lalita	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sukumar	-	-	-	-	-	-
Navprasuta	-	+	-	-	+	+
Some other conditions						
Ratrijagarana	-	-	+	-	-	-
Ravati	-	-	-	-	-	-
Anupnigdha	-	-	-	-	-	-
Atisnigdha	+	+	-	+	+	+
Atiruksha	+	-	-	-	+	+
Bhayopatapta	-	+	-	-	+	+
Chintaprasakta	+	-	-	-	+	+
Maithunaprasakta	+	-	-	-	-	-
Adhyayanaprasakta	+	-	-	-	-	-
Vyayamaprasakta	+	+	+	+	+	+
Shalyardita	+	-	+	+	-	-
Shosha	-	-	-	+	-	-

Kamadivyagraha	+	+	-	-	-	-
Niruda	+	-	-	-	-	-
Samavastha						
Navapratishtya	-	+	-	-	-	-
Navajwara	+	+	+	+	+	+
Disease of the rectum						
Kshataguda	+	+	+	-	-	-
Muktanala	+	-	+	-	-	-
Margavirodhi vyadhi						
Adhogarakta pitta	+	+	+	+	-	-
Atisara	-	-	-	+	-	-

Other diseases						
Madatyaya	+	+	+	-	+	+
Adhamana	+	+	+	-	-	-
Talushosha	-	-	-	-	-	-
Urusthambha	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ardita	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hanugraha	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hridroga	-	-	-	-	-	-
Kevala Vataroga	-	-	-	-	-	-
Rajyakshma	-	-	+	-	-	-

Classification of Virechana Drugs

According to the references the Virechana drugs may be classified in following groups;
Virechana drugs according to their origin and parts used [11],[12]

Animal Origin - Urine, Milk, Takra (Butter milk)

Plant Origin -

Mulini Drugs - The roots of the plants, which have been recommended for Virechana are Hastidanti, Shyamatrivrita, Adhoguda (Vidhara), Saptala, Pratyagasreni (Danti), Gavakshi, Vishanika, Ajagandha, Pravanti, Kshirini, Shankhini, Sruk, Svarnakshiri, Chitraka, Kinhi, Kusha and Kasha, Vacha, Hrasva Panchamula, both Punarnava, Vastak, Shak, Shala.

Phalani Drugs - Phalini drugs are mainly Shankhini, Vidanga, Anupa Klitaka, Sthalaja Klitaka, Abhaya, Antahkoterpshpi, Kampillaka and Aragwadha, Puga, Haritaki, Amalaki, Vibhitaki, Nilini, Chaturangula, Eranda, Kampillaka, Pilu, Priyal, Kubala, Badara, Karkandu, Kasmarya, Parusaka, Draksha etc.

Kshirini Drugs - Snuhi and Arka, Saptachhada, Jyotishmati.

Tvak - Barks of Putika, Tilvaka, Kampillaka, Ramyaka Patla etc.

Virechana Drugs According to Their Mode of Action [13]

Acharya Sharangadhara has classified the drugs from their mode of action. A group of drugs known as 'Virechanopaga' mentioned by Acharya Charaka, which may also be added to this classification, as a fifth group.

Anulomana: The drugs, which move the Malas downwards after digestion and breaking their bandha, are known as Anulomana. e.g. Haritaki

Sransana: The literary meaning of Sransana is to slip or to fall down. The drugs, which bring the semi-digested and sticky Malas without causing their digestion is known as Sransana. e.g. Aragwadha.

Bhedana: The Drugs which disintegrate the Abaddha (unformed) or Baddha (formed) or Pindita (dried focal mass) forms of Malas by facilitating penetration into it and then evacuating through the lower gut is known as Bhedana e.g. Katuki. Acharya Charaka has described a group of drug named as Bhedaniya. This includes Suvaha (Trivrit), Arka, Urubuka (Eranda), Agnimukhi (Kalihari), Chitra (Danti), Chitraka, Chirabilva, Sanhini, Shakuladani (Katuki) and Svarnakshiri.

Rechana: The drugs which eliminates Pakvam (digested) and Apakvam (undigested) Malas or Doshas by making them watery through the lower gut is known as Rechana. e.g. Trivrut.

Virechanopaga: The Virechanopaga Gana described in Charaka Samhita has been considered as helping in inducing Virechana. These are Draksha, Kasmarya, Parusaka, Abhaya, Amalaki, Bibhitaki, Badara, Karkandu and Pilu.

Virechana Drugs According to Intensity of Action

Mrudu Virechana: The Drugs, which are Manda in Virya, when combined with opposite Virya or given in low dose, given to Ruksha patient and causing less purgation is known as Mrudu Virechana. Charaka has the view that the physician should not hesitate to use Mrudu Virechana drugs in weak patients having more Doshas because repeated elimination of Doshas in small quantity may cure the disease.[14]

The patient who have not taken Virechana Drugs in past and whose Kostha is unknown in such patients Sushruta recommended the use of Mrudu Virechana drugs in the beginning and after knowing the Kostha required drug may be prescribed.[15]

Sharangadhara recommended that the Mrudu Virechana drugs i.e. Draksha, milk, warm water, castor oil etc. should be used in Mrudu Koshti patient.[16] Drugs effective in Mrudu Koshta are Guda, Sugar cane juice, Mastu, Ulloditadadhi, Payas, Kshira, Sarpi, Kashmari, Triphala, Pilu and Tarunamadya.[17]

Madhya Virechana: The drugs which are moderate in qualities are known as Madhya Virechana drugs. These drugs are specifically indicated in the patients having Madhya Roga (disease with moderate symptoms). The administration of these drugs in Balavana patient is useless, because they are unable to eliminate Doshas completely.[18]

Sharangadhara recommended the use of Trivrut, Katuki and Aragvadhya for Madhya Kostha.[19]

Tikshna Virechana: The drugs which cause Mahavega (numerous motions) and eliminates the Doshas in large quantity by Kshipra (quick) and gentle purgation causing neither much Glani (depression) nor pain in heart area or anus nor harmful to internal organs, is known as Tikshna Virechana.

Acharya Charaka recommended the use of these drugs in the Balvana Rogi, presenting all the symptoms of the disease i.e. Tikshana Vyadhi.[20] Snuhi Kshira is the best Tikshana Virechana drug among those drugs.[21]

Virechana From Ruksha And Snigdha Point of View

The drugs which are used in the form of oil or the preparation containing Sneha is known as Sneha Virechana e.g. Castor oil. Vagbhatta recommended the use of Sneha Virechana in all patients except Snigdha patient.[22] The use of Sneha Virechana in the patients who have taken higher dosage of Sneha is contraindicated because due to this the movable Doshas may again adhere in the Srotas.[23] The preparations, which do not contain Sneha, can be used as Ruksha Virechana. It has been recommended on the Snigdha patients who have comparatively taken more Sneha.[24]

According to Kalpana

This is for maintenance of active principle for longer period and convenience of taking drugs as – Churna, Vartikriya, Asava, Arishta, Avaleha, Sneha and Kashaya. According to Sushruta following 8 preparations are useful, Ghruta Yoga, Taila Yoga, Kshira Yoga, Madhya Yoga, Mutra Yoga, Mansarasa Yoga, Bhakshana Yoga and Avaleha Yoga. Kshira,

Rasa, Kalka, Kashaya, Kwatha, Shita are Laghu in descending order.[25]

Table 3: Virechana drugs according to season [26]

Rutu	Preparation	Anupana
Varsha	Trivrut Kutajabeej Pippali Shunthi	Draksha Rasa Madhu
Sharad	Trivrut	Draksa
	Duralabha	decoction
	Musta	
	Sharkara	
	Usheer	
	Chandana	
	Satala	
	Yashtimadhu	
Hemant	Trivrut	Ushna
	Chitraka	Jala
	Patha	
	Jivaka	
	Sarala	
	Vacha	
	Hemakshiri	
Shishir & Vasanta	Trivrut Pippali	Madhu
	Nagara	
	Sindhu	
	Shyama	
Grishma	Trivrut	Sharkara
All Seasons	Trivrut Danti Hapusha Saptala Katuki Swarna-	Gomutra

Dosage of Virechana Drugs

While describing the process of Virechana the dose of Trivrut mentioned is one Aksha (Tola).[27]

Table 4: According to Sharangadhara[28]

Kalpana	Hina for Mrudu Kostha	Madhyama for Madhyama Kostha	Uttam for Krura Kostha
Kwatha	2 Tola	4 Tola	8 Tola
Kalka, Churna, Modaka.	1 Tola	2 Tola	4 Tola

It is better to add Madhu before using these preparations.

According to Koshtha[29]

Mrudu, Madhyam and Tikshna Matras are mentioned for Mrudu, Madhyama and Krura Kostha respectively.

Procedure of Virechana Karma

This includes administration of Virechana Yogas, observation especially for Aushadha Jirnata, observation of Shuddhi Lakshanas and management of Vyapada if occurs.

Administration of Virechana Yoga

The Virechana Yoga is given to the patient

- After Samyaka Snehana and Svedana.
- While the patient is cheerful, slept well and has fully digested his previous meal.
- After assessing the psychological condition of the patient (Manasamabhisamikshya).
- Krita Homa, Bali etc. on Ishta Tithi, Muhurta.
- After Swastivachana.
- Virechana performed on empty stomach.[30]
- About the time of giving Virechana, Vagbhatta mentioned 'Shleshma Kalagate' means after passing Shleshma Kala i.e. after 10 A.M. but not before 9 A.M. in any case.[31]

4. Observations

Aushadha Jirna Lakshana

Aushadha Jirna Lakshana are Vatanulomana, Swasthya, Kshudha, Trishna, Urja, Manasvita, Indriya Laghuta.

Hrita Dosha Lakshana

The Virechana is considered as Kaphanta and Hritadosha when come out with Pitta and Kapha one by one in sequence. Gatradaurbalya and Laghuta are the associated symptoms.[32]

Shuddhi Lakshana

Four types of Shuddhi viz. Laingiki, Antiki, Vaigiki and Maniki should be observed according to Chakrapani, but the importance should be given to Laingiki Shuddhi.

Table 5: Antiki, Vaigiki and Maniki Shuddhi in Virechana Karma [33]

Shuddhi	Pravara	Madhyama	Avara
Vaigiki	30 Vega	20 Vega	10 Vega
Maniki	4 Prastha	3 Prastha	2 Prastha
Antiki	Kaphanta	Kaphanta	Kaphanta

Laingiki Shuddhi Lakshanas according to Acharyas are as follows,

Table 6: Samyaka Yoga Lakshana of Virechana Karma [34][35][36]

Lakshana	Charaka	Sushruta	Vagbhata
Indriya / Buddhi Prasada	+	+	+
Stroto Vishuddhi	+	-	-
Laghuta	+	-	+
Agnivridhi	+	+	-
Anamayatva	+	-	+
Kramat vit-Pitta- Kapha Agamana	+	-	+
Vata Anulomana	+	-	+

Table 7: Ayoga Lakshana of Virechana Karma [37][38][39]

Lakshana	Charaka	Sushruta	Vagbhata
Kapha Prakopa	+	+	+
Pitta Prakopa	+	+	+
Vata Prakopa	+	-	-
Agnimandya	+	+	-
Gaurava	+	+	-
Pratishyaya	+	-	+
Tandra	+	-	-
Chhardi	+	-	-
Aruchi	+	+	+
Vata Pratilomana	+	-	Vata vighraha
Daha	-	+	+
Hridaya Ashuddhi	-	+	+
Kukshi Ashuddhi	-	+	+
Kandu	-	+	+
Vitsanga	+	+	+
Mutrasanga	-	+	-
Pidika	-	-	+

Table 8: Atiyoga Lakshana of Virechana [40][41][42]

Lakshana	Charaka	Sushruta	Vagbhata
Kapha Kshaya Vikara	+	+	-
Pitta Kshaya Vikara	+	-	-
Vata Kshaya Vikara	+	-	-
Supti	+	-	-
Agnimandya	+	-	-
Klama	+	-	-
Vepathu	+	-	-
Nidra	+	-	-
Balabhava	+	-	-

Tamah Pravesha	+	-	-
Unmada	+	-	-
Hikka	+	-	-
Murchha	-	+	-
Gudabhransha	-	-	-
Kapha-Pitta Rahita Udaka Nihasarana	-	-	-
Kapha-Pitta Rahita Lohita Nihasarana	-	-	+
Mamsa Dhavanavata Udaka Srava	-	-	+
Medokhandavat Srava	-	-	+
Trushna	-	-	+
Bhrama	-	-	+
Netrapravesha	-	-	+
Raktakshayaja Vikara	+	-	-

Table 9: Virechana Vyapada with their treatment [43]

Vyapada	Lakshana	Chikitsa
Adhmana	Adhmana, Udavart, Nabhi, Prustha, Parshva,	Abhyanga, Sveda, Phalavarti, Niruha, Anuvasana, Udavarthara
	Shiraruja, Swasa, Vit-Mutra-Vata Sanga	Chikitsa
Parikartika I II III	Gudaparikartan Tivrashula, Piccha Rakta Mala Pravrutti	Laghana,Pachana Ruksha Ushna Bhojan Yastimadhu Sneha Basti
Paristrava	Alpamala Pravrutti, Kandu, Shopha, Kustha Gaurava, Agnimandya Staimitya, Aruchi, Pandu	Alpa Shamana Vamana,Virechana Grahani Chikitsa Asava, Arishta
Hridgraha	Hikka, Swasa, Kasa Parshvashula, Lalasrava Akshivibhrama, Shula Dantakitkitayan, Sadnyanasha	Snigdha Lavana Sveda,Yasti Taila Anuvasana,Tikshn Nasya,Vamana Basti
Angagraha	Stambha,Vepathu, Toda Pindikodveshtana Manthanavata Pida	Vataharachikitsa Snehana Svedana
Jivadana	Raktachandrikayu kta Udakasrava Gudabhransha, Trishna Murchha, Mada	Pittaharachikitsa Raktapana,Raktab asti, Pichha Basti Ghritamanda Anuvasan Basti

Vibhransh a. Guda b. Sanjya c. Kanduadi	Only mala excreted not Doshas, shodhana occur Gudabhransha Sangya Bhransha Kandu, Pidika Kustha roga	Kashaya lepa Snehana mrudusveda Manoanukul chi. Tikshna shodhana after snehapana
Stambha	Vatavarodha Gudastambha, Gudshula Alpa-mala pravrutti	Langhana, Pachana Tikshna Basti Virechana
Updrava	Stambha, Gatragraha, Sarvanga Vedana, Shula	Snehana, Svedana Vatahara Chikitsa
Klama	Tandra, Gaurava, Klama Daurbalya, Angasada	Langhana, Pachana Snehana, Tikshana Shodhana
Vamana by Virechana Yoga	Vamana	Snehana Svedana Virechana
Ayogya	Vibhransha, Hikka, Pindikodveshtana, Kandu, Urahshula Vaivarnyata	Roganusara Chikitsa Gomutra Niruhana
Atiyoga	Ati-Virechana	Mrudu Vamana Raktapittahara Vatahara Chikitsa

Mode of action of Virechana

Action of Virechana Karmas can be divided in the following two ways.

- 1) Systemic - By which it brings down the morbid Doshas, particularly Pitta from the Amashaya or Pakvashaya, i.e. G.I.T.
- 2) Local evacuant - It is concerned with the evacuation of these Doshas in the form of Malas from the gut by purgation.

Both the action and related factors are being described here in detail.

Virechana drugs gets absorbed and due to Virya, it reaches to the Hridaya (heart) then the Dhamanis and then after reaches to Sthula and Anu Srotas i.e. macro and micro channels of the body.

- The Vyavayi Guna of drug is responsible for quick absorption.
- The Vikasi Guna causes softening and loosening of the Bandha.
- Due to Ushna Guna, the Dosha Sanghata (compactness) is liquefied (Vishyandana).
- Action of Tikshna Guna is to break the Mala and Dosha in micro forms. According to Dalhana it is responsible for quick excretion.
- Due to Sukshma Guna, by reaching in micro channels, disintegrates endogenic toxins, which are then excreted through micro-channels (Anupravanabhava).
- Due to Prabhava mainly and also due to Pruthavi Jala constitution, finally Virechana occurs. This is the evacuation action.[44]

5. Discussion

Samhitas are oldest source of knowledge written before 3000 BC and which provide thorough knowledge of Ayurveda in Sanskrita. Samhitas guided us very well towards different subjects but Shodhana and Shamana therapies were primarily focused to treat various types of diseases. It became clear from screening of Samhitas that Shodhana therapies were widely elaborated but the references found in scattered manner. Out of five, Virechana is less stressful procedure. It has less possibility of complications and could be done easily. So, it is widely used as Shodhana therapy in routine. It is more acceptable to all classes of patients. In addition to the acceptability and popularity, the Virechana is considered as the best treatment for morbid and increased Pitta Dosha. So, it is the need of time to collect all references of Virechana at one place and to get its thorough knowledge at a glance.

6. Conclusion

Reviewing Samhitas revealed that use of Shodhana therapies especially Virechana is found to be used since long time. It is generally thought that Ayurveda classics i.e., Samhitas such as Charaka, Sushruta and Vagbhata have their major role in contribution of body detoxification procedures i.e., Shodhana therapies. From having looked at references mentioned in above article, it is clear that Samhitas dealt significantly in development of Shodhana therapies. Unfortunately, due to scattered form of references of Virechana, it has become difficult to establish proper method of body detoxification procedures. Therefore, it has become necessity to study Samhitas from various point of view of Ayurveda. This research paper was an attempt to study from Virechana perspective. Scholars would be delighted to know how immense research one can carry out in these Samhitas and bring new knowledge in front of the world.

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